

CALCULATIONS, MAIN ASSUPTIONS AND FINANCIAL SCHEME RELATED TO THE EXPECTED IMPACT OF MUDEJAR PROPOSAL

Section 1. JUSTIFICATION OF THE NUMBER OF PROJECTS AND VOLUME OF INVESTMENTS IN RELATION TO THE EXPECTED IMPACT EI1

This document presents the calculations and main assumptions that justify the expected impact (EI1) outlined in Section 2.1 regarding the development of 201 investment projects, totalling €4,691,612, across 11 Actions belonging to two categories: renewable energy and energy efficiency.

➤ **RENEWABLE ENERGY ACTIONS:** 24 Projects (€2,247,209) grouped into 5 Actions (Action 1 to 5):

MUDEJAR is aligned with CERCA's objective of operating up to 4 MWp of installed PV systems in the Calatayud region in the medium term. To achieve this, MUDEJAR proposes the following segmentation of PV energy generation projects:

- **12 PV self-consumption projects** in 12 villages for 12 Municipalities and 144 homes, totalling a power of **1.001 MWp**, including 10% of homes in energy poverty. **Investment volume: €575,379.** The following assumptions have been taken into account to achieve these figures: the average consumption of a home is estimated to be 10 kWh/day and that of city councils, 200 kWh/day. In addition, the average annual productivity of a well-south-oriented PV system is $Y_y = 1,400 \text{ kWh/kWp}$. Simple calculations show that the total annual energy demand (L_y) is 144 homes x 3.65 MWh/year·home + 12 city councils x 73 MWh/year·city council = **1,401.6 MWh/year**. The power required to meet this demand with PV systems (P_{PV}) is given by equation [1]:

$$P_{PV} = \frac{L_y}{Y_y} = \frac{1,401.6}{1,400.0} = 1.001 \text{ MWp} \quad [1]$$

The annual energy produced will be **1,401.6 MWh/year**, of which 40% is estimated to be self-consumed and 60% will be surpluses. These **12 projects** are divided into two categories:

- **(Action 1) 6 projects for the recovery of existing PV self-consumption installations** in 6 different villages in the Calatayud region, with an average power of 83.5 kWp/village. These systems are installed on municipal rooftops and are municipally owned. CERCA has identified over 20 such installations and has received requests from city councils to recover and refurbish them. Generally, these installations, between 1 and 12 years old, are in an unknown technical-operational state and are not activated as self-consumption systems, as stipulated in Royal Decree 244/2019¹. CERCA will sign an agreement with these city councils committing to make the necessary investments to recover, refurbish, legalise, and activate these installations as collective PV self-consumption systems, and in return, will have the right to operate them and manage energy surpluses. The average cost of recovery and refurbishment actions for these installations is **250 €/kWp**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 6 projects, totalling **0.501 MWp** of power, will be **€125,250**.

Of the 144 homes associated with collective self-consumption, **10%**, i.e., 15 homes, will have been previously identified as households in energy poverty. The annual electricity demand of these homes is **54.75 MWh/year** and their self-consumption will be associated with the facilities recovered in Action 1 projects. As a result, of the investment volume for Action 1 (€125,250), **€21,577.7** corresponds to these homes, which are linked to a PV power of **50.1 kWp**.

Impact during the project implementation: 2 projects for the recovery of existing PV self-consumption installations in 2 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.167 MWp. The necessary investment volume will be **€41,750**.

Impact up to 5 years after: 4 projects for the recovery of existing PV self-consumption installations in 4 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.334 MWp. The necessary investment volume will be **€83,500**.

¹ Real Decreto 244/2019, de 5 de abril, por el que se regulan las condiciones administrativas, técnicas y económicas del autoconsumo de energía eléctrica, publicado en el [BOE núm. 83, de 06/04/2019](https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2019-5089). <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-2019-5089>

- **(Action 2) 6 projects for new collective PV self-consumption systems** in 6 villages, installed on municipal or private rooftops, with an average power of 83.36 kWp each. The conservative average cost of a PV system of this power range installed on a rooftop is **900 €/kWp**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 6 projects, totalling **0.5001 MWp** of power, will be **€450,129**.
Impact during the project implementation: 2 projects for new collective PV self-consumption systems in 2 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.1667 MWp. The necessary investment volume will be **€150,043**.
Impact up to 5 years after: 4 projects for new collective PV self-consumption systems in 4 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.3334 MWp. The necessary investment volume will be **€300,086**.
- **(Action 3) Development of 6 PV Systems for Local Shops via PPAs**, installed on municipal or private building rooftops, under PPA (Power Purchase Agreement) energy sale models for **45 local shops and SMEs** distributed between Calatayud (20 shops) and 5 other villages in the region (25 shops, at a rate of 5 shops per village). The scenario considered is that the PV systems produce the same amount of annual energy as the total consumption of the shops associated with these PV self-consumption systems, i.e. 50 kWh/day on average. Using equation [1], the necessary power required to meet this demand with PV systems will be **0.5866 MWp**, distributed as 117.32 kWp for shops in Calatayud (13 kWp per shop) and 51.14 kWp in the other village. The annual energy produced by all systems will be **821.25 MWh/year**, of which 60% will be self-consumed through PPA contracts and 40% will be surpluses managed by CERCA. The conservative average cost of a PV system of this power range installed on a rooftop is **850 €/kWp**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 6 projects, totalling **0.5866MWp** of power, will be **€498,616**.
Impact during the project implementation: 2 PV Systems for Local Shops via PPAs in 2 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.1955 MWp. Necessary investment volume: **€166,205**.
Impact up to 5 years after: 4 PV Systems for Local Shops via PPAs in 4 different villages in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.3911 MWp. Necessary investment volume: **€332,411**.
- **(Action 4) Development of 6 PV Systems for Industrial Self-Consumption**, installed on industrial building rooftops located in 6 industrial estates in the Calatayud region for the PV self-consumption of 6 industries. As in previous actions, the scenario considered is that the PV systems produce the same amount of annual energy as the total consumption of the industries, i.e. 1,000 kWh/day on average. Therefore, the necessary power required to meet this demand with PV systems will be **1.5643 MWp**, distributed as an average power of 260.7 kWp per industrial estate. The annual energy produced by all systems will be **2,190 MWh/year**, of which 60% is estimated to be self-consumed and 40% will be surpluses managed by CERCA. The conservative average cost of a PV system of this power range installed on a rooftop is **750 €/kWp**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 6 projects, totalling **1.5643 MWp** of power, will be **€1,173,214**.
Impact during the project implementation: 2 PV Systems for Industrial Self-Consumption in 2 different industrial estates in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 0.5214 MWp. Necessary investment volume: **€391,071**.
Impact up to 5 years after: 4 PV Systems for Industrial Self-Consumption in 4 different industrial estates in the Calatayud region, totalling a power of 1.0429 MWp. Necessary investment volume: **€782,143**.
- **(Action 5) Monetising CERCA's Existing Solar Pipeline:** CERCA already has PV facilities with a capacity of **0.825 MWp** for self-consumption, distributed across **18 installations in 15 villages** in the Calatayud region. In total, **150 sites** benefit from these facilities, including homes, town halls, industrial sites and local shops. These PV systems have an average productivity rate of 1,400 kWh/kWp, meaning their combined annual production is **1,155 MWh**.

The ownership of all these PV energy generation infrastructures will belong to **CERCA**.

➤ **ENERGY EFFICIENCY ACTIONS: 177 Projects (€2,444,403) grouped into 6 Actions (Action 6 to 11)**

The JALON Project aimed to integrate **13.5% of the population and industries** of the Calatayud region into the renewable energy community, representing **5,000 citizens and 75 industries**, considered the early adopters (individuals willing to embrace innovation ahead of the majority) of the regional CER as a technological innovation system. Through its energy efficiency projects, MUDEJAR aims to reach **13.5% of people and industries** involved, i.e. **675 citizens (270 homes)** and **10 industries**. In addition, MUDEJAR proposes to include 2 more industries and 20 local shops as

beneficiaries of energy efficiency and energy storage projects. These individuals and organisations will become the new early adopters within the existing group of early adopters.

The projects developed in Actions 6, 7 and 8 generate **Energy Saving Certificates (ESCs)**, in accordance with current Spanish regulations². CERCA will provide a value-added service by managing the generation and monetisation of these ESCs, which will be an essential part of MUDEJAR's proposed financial scheme.

- **(Action 6) Development of 70 projects for the replacement of gas or gasoil heating systems with heat pumps in 70 homes**, generating energy and economic savings while improving comfort. The average profile of rural homes in the Calatayud region are old constructions of large surface area, averaging 150 m², and with deficient thermal insulation of their envelope. Most are labelled with letter E³ or higher on the building energy efficiency rating scale⁴ (E classification is in the mid-to-low part of a scale ranging from A to G, which considers factors such as annual CO_{2e} emissions, annual non-renewable primary energy consumption, and heating demand). To size the heat pump and calculate energy savings, the methodology presented in the catalogue of datasheets for the Energy Saving Certificates⁵ (ESCs) system has been used. The heating energy demand of the home according to the energy efficiency certificate before the intervention is 170 kWh/m² and the domestic hot water energy demand⁶ is 43.9 kWh/m². The performance of the fossil fuel boiler is 0.92. A seasonal coefficient of performance for the heat pump in heating SCOP=3.5 and for domestic hot water SCOP_{dhw}=2.5 is used. The primary energy saving obtained is **24.95 MWh/year/home**, i.e., **77.4%** compared to the previous fossil fuel boiler. The total saving for 70 homes will be **1,447.29 MWh/year**. The conservative cost of supplying and installing a heat pump for a 150 m² home is **€12,500**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 70 projects will be **€875,000**.

Impact during the project implementation: 12 projects for the replacement of gas or gasoil heating systems with heat pumps in 12 homes. Necessary investment volume: **€150,000**.

Impact up to 5 years after: 58 projects for the replacement of gas or gasoil heating systems with heat pumps in 58 homes. Necessary investment volume: **€725,000**.

The ownership of the heat pumps will belong to the homeowners.

- **(Action 7) Development of 70 projects** to improve the building envelope in residential buildings by **replacing old windows with new**, energy-efficient, double- or triple-glazed windows featuring low-emissivity coatings and thermal break frames, so as to contribute to reducing thermal transmittance, improving airtightness, and reducing heating and cooling demand. The same methodology described in the MITECO ESC system catalogue of datasheets is used to calculate energy savings and the necessary investment, starting from the same type of home described in the previous point. An average of 6 windows per home is considered, with an average surface area of 1.3 m²/window, meaning a total window area of 7.8 m²/home. Based on the *Código Técnico de la Edificación: Documento Básico HE. Ahorro de energía*⁷, for the geographical area of Calatayud, the transmittance of old windows is 5.7 W/m²K and that of new ones is 2 W/m²K. The climate zone coefficient corresponding to the Calatayud region is **46 thousand-hours-K/year**. With these data, the primary energy saving obtained through window replacement is **1.3 MWh/year/home**, i.e., **64.9%** corresponding to the building envelope of the home, compared to the initial situation. The average unit cost for supplying and installing windows is **800 €/m²**. For one home, this implies an investment volume of **€6,240**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 70 projects is **€436,800**.

Impact during the project implementation: 12 projects to improve the building envelope in 12 residential buildings. Necessary investment volume: **€74,880**.

Impact up to 5 years after: 58 projects to improve the building envelope in 12 residential buildings. Necessary investment volume: **€361,920**.

The ownership of the new windows will belong to the homeowners.

² Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. (2023, 24 de enero). *Real Decreto 36/2023, de 24 de enero, por el que se establece un sistema de Certificados de Ahorro Energético*. Boletín Oficial del Estado, n.º 21, 10349-10372. Referencia BOE-A-2023-2027.

³ Ministerio de Vivienda y Agenda Urbana. (s.f.). *URBAN3R: Sistema de gestión del suelo urbano*. <https://urban3r.es/>

⁴ IDAE. (2015). Calificación de la eficiencia energética de los edificios. Recuperado de MITECO <https://energia.gob.es/desarrollo/EficienciaEnergetica/CertificacionEnergetica/DocumentosReconocidos/normativamodelosutilizacion/20151123-Calificacion-eficiencia-energetica-edificios.pdf>

⁵ Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. (s.f.). *Catálogo de Fichas CAE*. <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/energia/eficiencia/cae/catalogo-de-fichas.html>

⁶ Ministerio de Fomento. (2019). *Código Técnico de la Edificación: Documento Básico HE. Ahorro de energía*. <https://www.codigotecnico.org/images/stories/pdf/ahorroEnergia/DBHE.pdf>

- (Action 8) Development of 23 projects for installing electric vehicle (EV) chargers** in the region. The objective of this measure is to replace 23 fossil fuel vehicles with electric ones, each of which is associated with three households. This will affect a total of 70 households. To achieve this, citizens willing to make the necessary investment for this replacement will be identified in the different villages of the region through surveys. In those villages where these individuals are identified, CERCA will install EV chargers. This vehicle replacement will generate Energy Saving Certificates (ESC) for the user, which will be managed and monetised by CERCA, investing the capital in the charging infrastructures. In return, users who have generated these ESCs will receive discounts on the use of charging points until the capital generated by the certificates is amortised. The energy saving generated by replacing a petrol vehicle that consumes 6 l/100 km with an electric one that consumes 18.6 kWh/100 km and has an average mileage of 20,000 km/year, is **7.3 MWh/year**, i.e., **66.3%**, according to the methodology described in the MITECO ESC system catalogue of datasheets. The conservative average cost of supplying and installing a three-phase charging point (11 kW – 22 kW) is **€3,000**⁷. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 23 projects is **€69,000**.

Impact during the project implementation: 4 projects for installing electric vehicle (EV) chargers. Necessary investment volume: **€12,000**.

Impact up to 5 years after: 19 projects to improve the building envelope in 12 residential buildings. Necessary investment volume: €57,000.

The ownership of the electric vehicle chargers will belong to **CERCA**.
- (Action 9) Development of 2 projects for improving industrial refrigeration processes in fruit industry companies.** According to data from the ESC Report – May 2025⁸, published by MITECO: the 2,282 actions carried out in Spain in that month generated a total of **1,119 GWh** of energy savings, i.e., an average of **490 MWh/action**, equivalent to an approximate saving of **30%**, as indicated by some specialised sources in this sector⁹. Based on the experience of MUDEJAR's partner ASIC XXI, an industry of this type, located in the Calatayud region, that implements a standardised energy efficiency measure in industrial refrigeration applications, can generate an average annual saving of **490 MWh**. These savings, converted into ESCs, taking a conservative ESC price of **135 €/MWh**, generate estimated revenues of **€66,150**, which is equivalent, depending on the type of installation and action, to between 10% and 30% of the investment made. Following the conservative trend, if we consider that the income generated by ESCs accounts for, on average, 15% of the investment required for improving industrial refrigeration processes, the investment volume needed for one industry will be **€441,000**. Therefore, the investment volume required for these 2 projects to improve energy efficiency in industries will be **€882,000**.

Impact during the project implementation: this action will be developed during the 5 years after the end of the projects. Therefore, it will have no impact during project implementation.

Impact up to 5 years after: 2 projects for improving industrial refrigeration processes in fruit industry companies. Necessary investment volume: **€882,000**.

The ownership of the new energy efficiency improvement elements in industrial refrigeration processes will belong to the industries themselves.
- (Action 10) Implementation of 2 projects for installing centralised batteries in 2 municipalities** of the region, where collective PV self-consumption systems exist, with a total capacity of **0.5 MWh**. MUDEJAR proposes the installation of these batteries under the **"Batteries-as-a-service" business model**. In this model, CERCA invests in installing these energy storage systems and offers local businesses and homes access to electricity storage without the need for an initial investment. In exchange for an affordable monthly fee, **20 local businesses and 60 homes** (50 of which are already CERCA prosumers and 10 of which have electricity supply contracts with CERCA) can benefit from cheap energy during the day when grid electricity tariffs are most expensive. The objective is to shift part of the PV production to hours when there is no solar generation, i.e., 50% of the daily energy consumed in homes and 20% of the energy consumed in businesses, assuming their daily consumption is 10 and 50 kWh/day respectively. A simple calculation shows that the total storage capacity is obtained from: 50% x 10 kWh/day/home x 60 homes + 20% x 50 kWh/day/business x 20 businesses = **500 kWh**. During periods of surplus battery capacity due to low demand, which we estimate to average 15%, additional income can be

⁷ <https://emovili.com/blog/precio-instalacion-cargador-coche/>

⁸ Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico. (2025, mayo). *Informe CAE – Mayo 2025*. Secretaría de Estado de Energía, Dirección General de Planificación y Coordinación Energética, Subdirección General de Eficiencia y Acceso a la Energía.

⁹ <https://www.ucersa.com/noticias/eficiencia-energetica-industrial-soluciones-clave-para-reducir-costes-y-emisiones#:~:text=Los%20ahorros%20pueden%20oscilar%20entre%20un%2015,de%20mantenimiento%2C%20paradas%20t%C3%A9cnicas%20y%20consumos%20auxiliares.>

generated through flexibility services such as day-ahead and intraday arbitrage, mFRR/aFRR balancing market availability and local grid support commissioned by the DSO. The annual amount of PV energy shifted thanks to the batteries will be **81.9 MWh/year** for the 60 homes and **54.6 MWh/year** for the 20 local businesses, taking into account that 15% is used for energy arbitrage and that the daily battery charge and discharge cycles have a round-trip efficiency of 88%. The unit cost for batteries with a capacity of 250 kWh is **250 €/kWh**. Therefore, to develop these two centralised battery projects, an investment of **500 kWh x 250 €/kWh = €125,000** is necessary.

Impact during the project implementation: **2 projects** for installing centralised batteries in 2 municipalities in the region to use them as "Batteries-as-a-service", with a total capacity of **500 kWh**. Necessary investment volume: **€125,000**.

Impact up to 5 years after: this action will be developed during the project implementation. Therefore, the impact in the 5 years after its end will be the same than during the project implementation.

The ownership of the centralised batteries will belong to **CERCA**.

- **(Action 11) Development of 10 projects for activating industrial flexibility** through the **Active Demand Response Service (SRAD)** of a 1 MW unit, formed by the aggregation of 10 industries, each making 0.1 MW available.. In 2025, this service has been remunerated in Spain at a price of **56.43 €/MW**, with 4,371 hours of service provision. In our case, this would generate a yearly income of **1 MW x 56.43 €/MW x 4,371 hours = 246,656 €**. It is expected that **15%** of the income generated by the SRAD will go to CERCA for this service (**€36,998**). CERCA will finance the installation of the necessary telemetry system for sending real-time information to the system operator (SO) through the generation and demand control centre. The average cost of this system is **5,007 €**, so the investment volume required to develop these 5 projects is **€50,070**.

Impact during the project implementation: this action will be developed during the 5 years after the end of the projects. Therefore, it will have no impact during this phase.

Impact up to 5 years after: **10 projects** for activating industrial flexibility through the Active Demand Response Service (SRAD). Necessary investment volume: **€50,070**.

The ownership of the telemetry systems will belong to the industries themselves.

Section 2. MUDEJAR FINANCIAL SCHEME

Actions	CAPEX (€)	VAT (21%) (€)	Financing sources							10 years monetised guarantees and de-risking instruments (€)							On-bill loans repayment	TOTAL						
			F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	G3	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	DR1			DR2	DR3				
Renewable energy	A1	103,673	21,771		40%	21%		60%		0%				338,355			31,563			X			42,610	412,528
	A1*	21,577	4,531			21%	40%		60%	0%				75,126			7,008			X			9,019	91,153
	A2	450,129	94,527		40%	21%			60%		0%			337,776			31,509			X			185,003	554,288
	A3	498,616	104,709		60%	21%	40%				0%			750,623			41,063			X				791,685
	A4	1,173,214	246,375		40%	21%			60%		0%			1,016,160			109,500	131,400		X		X	482,191	1,739,251
A5	0	-0								0%			619,178			57,759			X					676,937
Energy efficiency	A6	875,000	183,750	15,0%		21%	11%	20%		34,8%	19,0%					237,555				X			228,189	465,743
	A7	436,800	91,728	15,0%		21%	30%	20%		34,8%	0,3%					12,638				X			199,338	211,976
	A8	69,000	14,490	15,0%	20%	21%	27%				34,8%	3,3%				22,859				X			43,448	66,308
	A9	888,533	186,592	15,0%		21%	20%	20%		34,8%	10,5%					133,280				X			346,018	479,298
	A10	125,000	26,250		60%	21%	40%				0%			182,281						X				182,281
	A11	50,070	10,515		60%	21%	40%				0%				369,983					X				369,983
Total (€)	4,691,612	985,239	340,400	1,108,818	985,239	699,872	1,476,276	12,946	790,165	263,134			3,319,499	369,983	406,332	278,402	131,400						1,535,815	6,041,431

- A1. Recovery of Underutilised Municipal PV Systems
- A1*. Corresponding low-income households
- A2. New Collective Self-Consumption Systems
- A3. PV Systems for Local Shops via PPAs
- A4. PV Systems for Industrial Self-Consumption
- A5. CERCA's Existing Solar Pipeline (0.825 MWp)
- A6. Replace diesel heating systems with electric heat pumps
- A7. High-performance window replacements
- A8. Sustainable Mobility Infrastructure
- A9. Industrial Cooling System Upgrades
- A10. Community-Scale Storage Systems
- A11. Activation of Industrial Flexibility via SRAD

- F1 Public grant programmes (non-reimbursable subsidies)
- F2 Senior bank debt
- F3 Bridge loan (short-term bank facility)
- F4 Crowdfunding (reimbursable citizen financing via platform)
- F5 Member equity through the REC
- F6 Impact equity via regional NGOs (on behalf of vulnerable households)
- F7 Energy-Efficiency Blended Fund (partially revolving)
- G1 Monetisation of Future Cash Flows (PV + BaaS)
- G1.1 O&M fees
- G1.2 Power Purchase Agreements with end-users (PPAs)
- G1.3 Surplus energy sales
- G1.4 Battery as a Service (BaaS) fees
- G1.5 Guarantees of Origin
- G2 Allocation of Active Demand Response Services (SRAD)
- G3 Energy Savings Certificates (ESCs)
- G4 On-Bill Financing Mechanisms. Contribution to the EEBF
- G5 Energy credits
- DR1 Surplus Price Insurance
- DR2 Energy Saving Insurance (ESI)
- DR3 Hedging mechanisms for Industrial PV surplus Credits

